

SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF THE FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGICAL CULTURE IN STUDENTS

Vakhabova O'g'iloy Talibjonovna

Teacher of the Department of Pedagogy and Psychology of the Andijan State Pedagogical
Institute

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Abstract. *In the article, the socio-psychological characteristics of the dynamics of the development of social intelligence in the process of professional formation of students are studied, the problems that arise in professional formation and the problems that arise in professional formation and the development of psychological culture of students, the image of "I" is correct. has been analyzed.*

Keywords: *intelligence, mental abilities, social and emotional intelligence, empathic abilities, dynamics of intelligence, social activity, "I" image.*

СОЦИАЛЬНО-ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ФАКТОРЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ СТУДЕНТОВ

Аннотация. *В статье исследуются социально-психологические особенности динамики развития социального интеллекта в процессе профессионального становления студентов, проблемы, возникающие при профессиональном становлении и проблемы, возникающие при профессиональном становлении и развитии психологической культуры. у студентов образ «Я» верен. был проанализирован.*

Ключевые слова: *интеллект, умственные способности, социально-эмоциональный интеллект, эмпатические способности, динамика интеллекта, социальная активность, образ «Я».*

INTRODUCTION

The role of the spiritual factor is great in increasing the social activity of young people in society, determining their role and place in life. It is one of the most complex and urgent problems of the present day to substantiate this from a scientific and theoretical point of view and to develop programs designed to educate spiritually rich young people in practice. As the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, noted, "... in today's violent times, only a truly spiritual and enlightened person knows the value of a person, understands his national values, national identity, lives in a free and free society, can selflessly fight for our independent country to take its rightful place in the world community". That is why it is becoming a vital need to study the political and practical nature of the spiritual factor and the problems of its influence on the growth of social activity of young people. In order not to create a void in the spiritual world of our youth, it is necessary to form a healthy way of life, respect for national and national values in their hearts and minds from childhood. In order to understand and understand spirituality, one must first understand and understand a person. That is why it is extremely important to pay attention to the problem of motivation, which explains human behavior, as an urgent problem today.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The fourth year of the "Strategy of actions on five priority areas of further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021" adopted by the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev No. PF-4947 dated February 7, 2017 "...increasing

technical education and strengthening the provision of highly qualified personnel in the field" The idea of freedom of the person and his intellectual potential is one of the main ones in the fulfillment of this task. Already, a free person, a free people, is able to actively act in the process of creativity, prosperity, humanitarianism, creativity, science, culture and modern production and achieve the intended goals. At the present time, the sharp changes in the development of the society impose qualitatively new and relatively complex tasks, in which the level of development of a person's intellect, the regulator of his mental capabilities, and moral aspects are of particular importance. So, how are these characteristics manifested and formed during the student period? One of the main features of the student period is the rapid realization of social maturity. Such maturity requires a person to acquire the necessary mental abilities, various roles to be performed in life and work. Mental maturity (maturity) is especially important. A student's timely attendance at classes and completion of assigned tasks cannot be the basis for the dynamics of intellectual development, which is not sufficient for diagnosing mental development [1]. Researching the nature of social intelligence of young people, scientifically in-depth analysis is the demand of today, it is important to study the methods of determining social intelligence and analyze its dynamics in the education of a mature generation, increase its intellectual potential and professional formation.

RESULTS

Now, if we analyze the image of "I" as one of the social factors affecting the development of students' psychological culture, psychologists conditionally indicate four interrelated aspects in terms of its construction:

1. Self-knowledge.
2. Self-attitude.
3. Self-awareness.
4. Self-influence.

For students, each of these covers different opportunities. But self-knowledge is the source of self-awareness and others. Self-knowledge as a whole determines the content of work on oneself, the program of self-education. At the same time, it is necessary to draw up a detailed program of the person, to achieve the corresponding goals and ideals that are brought up in students [2]. So, self-awareness based on self-knowledge, in general, can lead to self-management and education. But the role of self-relation should not be overlooked. Therefore, we will consider what different aspects of self-awareness can contribute to self-management and education. Self-relation, which is a valuable aspect of self-awareness, implies that a person is treated as a different person. First of all, it includes a person's orientation (goals, ideals, needs, interests), orientation of values to spiritual values, self-demand, self-expression. Self-attitude is always about self-awareness. Self-esteem, in turn, is related to self-expression and self-affirmation. The mental state of a person, expressed by self-satisfaction or dissatisfaction, creates an internal environment with his behavior, and the internal environment, in turn, affects all aspects of the human "I" [3]. Therefore, the plan of self-improvement largely depends on self-knowledge and attitude towards self. If the student is able to express himself correctly, to approach his actions critically and objectively, then there is still a need for self-education. Self-awareness and self-influence are manifested as the emotional-emotional aspect of self-awareness.

DISCUSSION

The emotional-emotional aspect of self-awareness includes such components and components as the ability to manage interests, desires, moods. All this is manifested to one degree or another in managing and justifying one's emotions and thoughts, behavior, and self-education. The interrelationship and interdependence of self-awareness and self-management can be visualized in the following diagram: . Many studies show that the image of "I" is not formed in a person quickly, but is formed as a result of social influences throughout his life. From the point of view of social psychology, we are interested in the way in which a person joins different social groups.

In many scientific sources, self-awareness is defined as follows: "A person's awareness, evaluation of his own knowledge, spiritual image and interests, ideals and moral motives, feeling and thinking as a person. to make a holistic assessment as a being, to separate oneself from the objective world, to understand and evaluate one's relationship to the universe, to understand oneself as a person, to understand one's actions, thoughts and feelings, desires and interests"[4]. A person's self-concept is age- and gender-specific. For example, extreme curiosity about oneself, the desire to know and understand who one is, develops especially during adolescence. The feeling of "adulthood" that appears in this period determines not only the attitude towards oneself, but also the relationship with others in both girls and teenage boys. The good and positive image of "I" in girls depends more on the ability of this image to embody feminine qualities, on the fact that feminine qualities are present at the same time, while the image in boys is more based on the criteria of physical perfection. depends on how well it fits. That is why, in adolescence, boys' low height, weak muscles and the image of "I" built on this basis cause a number of negative impressions. In girls, the image of "I" is perceived meaningfully, depending on external beauty, elegance, manners, and the presence of a number of other feminine qualities. Even in girls, excess weight or certain rashes on the skin or similar physiological defects cause strong negative emotions, but beautiful clothes, jewelry or a unique hair style are considered as factors that overcome these defects. However, it is worth mentioning that the external environment surrounding that person, others and their attitude play a big role in the positive or negative image of "I". A person looks at others and imagines himself as if he sees himself in a mirror. This process is called reflection in psychology. Its essence is to form an image of oneself through the image of people similar to oneself. L. S. Kohn analyzes these thoughts in his work entitled "Creation of the Self" and says that "a person first of all understands the qualities that draw attention to himself." According to D. Mead, self-awareness is looking at oneself through the eyes of people united by joint activity. A.N. Leontev thinks about the role of social activity in self-awareness and says: "Individual "I" is a social composition resulting from social skills according to its composition" [5].

There are a number of other considerations regarding the self-awareness of a person, the main fact in its study is that it does not arise like simple descriptions, but it is considered one of the important factors of a person's education and upbringing. From this point of view, education can be defined as the process of formation of ideas about the person himself and his qualities. Therefore, the more clearly each person knows and can imagine himself, the less likely he is to act against the norms of society, and then he is considered a well-educated person.

Only the growth of mental intelligence is not enough for the psychological maturity of students. In the formation of a specialist, each student is not only a subject capable of acquiring the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities for his field, but he is flexible in social relations,

able to feel the experiences of others, and has an influence on them. , the issue of the need to be a psychologically mature person who is able to enter into relationships and adapt his behavior to others, remained a cross-sectional issue.

CONCLUSIONS

In short, the results of social intelligence, which is a component of students' psychological maturity, are necessary to ensure the psychological maturity of the students, along with specific social and psychological measures, as well as independent research on their personal qualities. One of the main tasks of social intelligence is the formation of long-term relationships. Understanding the level and character of mutual relations is to positively influence each other and strengthen relations in the future.

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